

Teacher Education And Methods For Teaching Life Skills.**Dr. Vilas B. Bandgar**

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Abstract:

Life skills have been defined as “the abilities for adaptive and positive behavior that enable individuals to deal effectively with the demands and challenges of everyday life” (WHO).

‘Adaptive’ means that a person is flexible in approach and is able to adjust in different circumstances. ‘Positive behavior’ implies that a person is forward looking and even in difficult situations, can find a ray of hope and opportunities to find solutions. The terms ‘Livelihood skills’ or occupational/ vocational skills refer to capabilities, resources and opportunities to pursue individual and household economic goals and relate to income generation. Thus, Life skills are distinct from livelihood skills.

Introduction:

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Key Life Skills Life skills include psychosocial competencies and interpersonal skills that help people make informed decisions, solve problems, think critically and creatively, communicate effectively, build healthy relationships, empathize with others, and cope with managing their lives in a healthy and productive manner. Essentially, there are two kinds of skills - those related to thinking termed as "thinking skills"; and skills related to dealing with others termed as "social skills". While thinking skills relate to reflection at a personal level, social skills include interpersonal skills and do not necessarily depend on logical thinking. It is the combination of these two types of skills that are needed for achieving assertive behavior and negotiating effectively. “Emotional” can be perceived as a skill not only in making rational decisions but also in being able to make others agree to one's point of view. To do that, coming to terms first with oneself is important. Thus, self-management is an important skill including managing/coping with feelings, emotions, stress and resisting peer and family pressure. Young people as advocates need both thinking and social skills for consensus building and advocacy on issues of concern.

Objectives:

1. To know what is mean by life skills?
2. To suggest methods of teaching life skills.

Life Skills Education:

The Ten core Life Skills as laid down by WHO are:

1. Self-awareness
2. Empathy
3. Critical thinking
4. Creative thinking
5. Decision making
6. Problem Solving
7. Effective communication
8. Interpersonal relationship
9. Coping with stress
10. Coping with emotion

- **Self-awareness:** self- awareness includes recognition of ‘self’, our character, our strengths and weaknesses, desires and dislikes. Developing self-awareness can help us to recognize when we are stressed or feel under pressure. It is often a prerequisite to effective communication and interpersonal relations, as well as for developing empathy with others.
- **Empathy:** Empathy To have a successful relationship with our loved ones and society at large, we need to understand and care about other peoples’ needs, desires and feelings. Empathy is the ability to imagine what life is like for another person. Without empathy, our communication with others will

amount to one-way traffic. Worst, we will be acting and behaving according to our self-interest and are bound to run into problems. No man is an island, no woman either! We grow up in relationships with many people – parents, brothers and sisters, cousins, uncles and aunts, classmates, friends and neighbors. When we understand ourselves as well as others, we are better prepared to communicate our needs and desires. We will be more equipped to say what we want people to know, present our thoughts and ideas and tackle delicate issues without offending other people. At the same time, we will be able to elicit support from others, and win their understanding. Empathy can help us to accept others, who may be very different from ourselves. This can improve social interactions, especially, in situations of ethnic or cultural diversity. 5 Empathy can also help to encourage nurturing behavior towards people in need of care and assistance, or tolerance, as is the case with AIDS sufferers, or people with mental disorders, who may be stigmatized and ostracized by the very people they depend upon for support.

- **Critical thinking:** Critical thinking is an ability to analyze information and experiences in an objective manner. Critical thinking can contribute to health by helping us to recognize and assess the factors that influence attitudes and behavior, such as values, peer pressure and the media.
- **Creative thinking:** Creative thinking is a novel way of seeing or doing things that is characteristic of four components – fluency (generating new ideas), flexibility (shifting perspective easily), originality (conceiving of something new), and elaboration (building on other ideas).
- **Decision making:** Decision making helps us to deal constructively with decisions about our lives. This can have consequences for health. It can teach people how to actively make decisions about their actions in relation to healthy assessment of different options and, what effects these different decisions are likely to have.
- **Problem solving:** Problem solving helps us to deal constructively with problems in our lives. Significant problems that are left unresolved can cause mental stress and give rise to accompanying physical strain.
- **Interpersonal relationship:** Interpersonal relationship skills help us to relate in positive ways with the people we interact with. This may mean being able to make and keep friendly relationships, which can be of great importance to our mental and social well-being. It may mean keeping, good relations with family members, which are an important source of social support. It may also mean being able to end relationships constructively.
- **Effective communication:** Effective communication means that we are able to express ourselves, both verbally and non-verbally, in ways that are appropriate to our cultures and situations. This means being able to express opinions and desires, and also needs and fears. And it may mean being able to ask for advice and help in a time of need.
- **Coping with stress:** coping with stress means recognizing the sources of stress in our lives, recognizing how this affects us, and acting in ways that help us control our levels of stress, by changing our environment or lifestyle and learning how to relax.
- **Â Coping with emotions:** A coping with emotions means involving recognizing emotions within us and others, being aware of how emotions influence behavior and being able to respond to emotions appropriately. Intense emotions like anger or sadness can have negative effects on our health if we do not respond appropriately.

Many life skills are required to manage a particular situation effectively. In a way various life skill work best in conjugation. In fact, the appropriate combination of life skills in a given moment is an art. Children learn their life skill from parents, teachers and significant others who act as their role model. They gradually learn to use a particular skill effectively in diverse situation to cope with challenges of life.

Different Methods that can be used to enhance Life Skills in Students:

Each method is specially designed to impact a particular skill skills and involves all or some of the following techniques:

Class Discussion: There are many benefits to the student-centered class discussion although it's sometimes a challenge to develop. There are a number of potential pitfalls, including students talking off-topic, not talking at all, or one or two students dominating the discussion.

Keys for Class Discussion: The Basics

1. Preparation
2. Not Alone
3. Provide A Stepping Stone
4. Set The Rules

5. Assign Roles Or Tasks
6. Tick-Tock
7. What's In It For Them
8. Beyond the Basic
9. Rubrics Help
10. Freedom

Brainstorming: Brainstorming is a method for generating ideas to solve a design problem. It usually involves a group, under the direction of a facilitator. The strength of brainstorming is the potential participants have in drawing associations between their ideas in a free-thinking environment, thereby broadening the solution space.

Role Playing: Role playing is a learning structure that allows students to immediately apply content as they are put in the role of a decision maker who must make a decision regarding a policy, resource allocation, or some other outcome. This technique is an excellent tool for engaging students and allowing them to interact with their peers as they try to complete the task assigned to them in their specific role. This work can be done in cooperative groups and/or students can maintain the persona of their role throughout the class period. Students are more engaged as they try to respond to the material from the perspective of their character.

Advantages of role playing

Students immediately apply content in a relevant, real world context.

Students take on a decision making persona that might let them diverge from the confines of their normal self-imposed limitations or boundaries.

Students can transcend and think beyond the confines of the classroom setting.

Students see the relevance of the content for handling real world situations.

The instructor and students receive immediate feedback with regard to student understanding of the content.

Students engage in higher order thinking and learn content in a deeper way.

Instructors can create useful scenarios when setting the parameters of the role play when real scenarios or contexts might not be readily available.

Typically students claim to remember their role in these scenarios and the ensuing discussion long after the semester ends.

Steps and tips for using role playing

Offer a relevant scenario to students. This scenario should include the role the student must play, the informational details relevant for decision making in this role, and a task to complete based on the information. This information might be provided on the screen through power point or by using a handout. It is highly recommended that the instructions be provided in writing so it is clear to students what they must do and how?

Give students five to ten minutes to complete the task. The instructor might have students do this alone or in small groups or follow the think-pair-share format in which students work individual and then discuss their results with their partner.

Find a way to process student deliberations. The instructor might ask students to write their replies to submit or this might be a very good lead in to a larger class discussion where students can justify their differing outcomes or opposing views.

Playing a story

You can play a story as it would be presented to an audience. There are controls for you to navigate back and forth through the slides. On a slide with a live data sheet inserted, you must first click the sheet before you can start making selections in it.

Debates:

In debates, a particular problem or issue is presented to the class and students must take a position on resolving the problem or issue. The class can debate as a whole or in a small group.

Steps in debates

1. Step 1: Brainstorm ideas
2. Step 2: Organize ideas
3. Step Three: Structure the speeches
4. Step 4: Prepare your speeches
5. Step 5: Prepare the rest of the class

Games and simulation:Contact a consultant in the to incorporate games or simulations into course learning activities. The CTL interactive-design team works with faculty members to either create custom interactive materials or recommend existing tools that best suits their needs. Incorporating games and simulations into courses can provide many benefits, including:

1. **Allowing students to learn by doing:** Interactive simulations provide a way for students to become active participants in the learning process and learn from their mistakes in a low-stakes, safe environment.
2. **Keeping students engaged:** Games and simulations can provide a valuable supplement to traditional instructional methods that keep students engaged and deliver course content to a wider variety of learning styles.
3. **Expanding learning beyond the classroom:** Games and simulations allow students to practice concepts and skills from any location

Conclusion:

Life skills include different competence and skills that help student make informed decisions, solve problems, think critically and creative, communicate effectively, build healthy relationship, empathize with others and cope with managing their lives in healthy and productive manner.

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